

Parents' Involvement Effect on Students' Academic Achievement and Quality Education in Public and Private Schools at Elementary Level

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Abstract

The purpose of this research was to check the participation of parents in the educational activities of their children and the meetings with the teachers and their effects on the students' academic achievement. The research was survey type and mixed method approach. For this purpose, total 30 students and six teachers were selected for sample. Data collected through a Likert scale from students and take interviews with teachers, data was interpreted through SPSS and NVivo. It was concluded that parental involvement in educational activities significantly effects on children's academic achievement.

Keywords: parent-teacher meetings, parents' involvement, academic achievement; private elementary schools; motivation, quality education

Introduction

Elementary school education has become a huge problem in Pakistan at present. Because children then go to secondary school and choose major subjects instead of core education. Therefore, elementary education provides a nursery, based on which children move on to

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arts, science, or vocational education in secondary education. Therefore, the quality of education at the elementary level is very important (Idrees et al., 2021; Hussain et al., 2022). The Ministry of Education has abolished the board examinations of primary and elementary education and allowed schools to conduct self-exams, due to which there has been a huge gap in the quality of education up to the elementary level (Wajid et al., 2022; Amir et al., 2022; Hussain et al., 2021).

In Pakistan, commercial education is now being given to the elementary level; many private educational institutions teach children up to the elementary level. Those working side by side with public schools (Carneiro et al., 2022; Hussain et al., 2021). The government only runs public schools, private educational institutions are self-supporting, and their main source is child fees. If you look at the outlook of private schools, it is very charming; cleanliness, children's uniform, timetable, homework, diary work, portfolio, and discipline are of a very high level (Hussain et al., 2022). On the contrary, the lack of this thing has been seen in public schools; the Government of Pakistan does not spend much on public schools, nor are repairs done.

It has often been seen that there is a lot of parental involvement in private schools. Parents studying in private schools have more touch with their children, but parents of children studying in public schools have less touch with their children (Ribeiro et al., 2021). Parents of children studying in private schools are more socialized or richer; to maintain their status, they teach their children in private schools with expensive fees and also stay in touch with the children (Hussain et al., 2022). To satisfy the parents, the private schools hold a meeting with the parents in the schools and present the results of the children to them; a program is organized during the meeting with the parents, and the children are also given certificates of appreciation (Ahmed et al., 2022).

Children whose parents are more in touch with them have better results. Parents keep knowing their children's performance, so they pay attention to the children. Help them do their homework or take a tutor at home to do their homework, which greatly improves the children's performance. The education and experience of the teachers in private schools are very less; on the contrary, the teachers and administration of public schools have a lot of experience. Children are not given any help to complete their homework at home because the parents are not aware of the actual situation of the children. Parents of children studying in public schools are often illiterate, so they do not know the educational situation. They send the children to fetch groceries for the house, or they cannot schedule the child's playtime (Boylan et al., 2021; Amir et al., 2021).

Encouraging children to enroll in private schools is done by charming the school; the buildings of private schools attract parents a lot, cleanliness, children's uniforms, children learn cultural songs, and children are kept busy in school for a long time (Taie & Goldring, 2020). They make art and designs from children, memorize Islamic verses, and teach them to speak in English, which makes parents very happy. Private schools often adopt many methods of charging fees; often, they make the children memorize only a few topics well for two or three days instead of the whole chapter and then take their test. If the result is good, they give the test to the child to ask the parents. Sign it so that the parents will be happy to see the good result; if the result is a little weak, then they hold a meeting of the parents and put all the responsibility on the parents, even if it is the teacher's fault. Still, all the

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responsibility is assigned to the parents (Paul et al., 2021). Parents teach their children properly, tutoring or giving their own time, in this way parental participation in children greatly improves the academic performance of children, on the contrary, there is no such scene in public schools, parents do not take any interest, and neither performs children. It is detected, and the results for the children are very poor (Triroso et al., 2022; Otani, 2020).

Current Study

This research was about parents' involvement in children's educational activities. This research examined the effects of parents' involvement in educational activities and their impacts on children's academic achievement. A review of previous research found that parental involvement in children's academic activities improves children's academic performance. The research aimed to check parental involvement in children's educational activities to improve children's academic achievement. The results of this research would be very useful for parents, teachers, and children.

Objectives of Study

1. This research aimed to evaluate the parents' involvement in children's educational activities and their effects on children's academic achievement.
2. The purpose of this research was also that the parents do not participate in the children's educational activities; what are their reasons?

Research Questions

1. Does parental involvement in schools and children's educational activities affect children's academic performance and achievement?
2. Are parents equally involved in children's educational activities in public and private schools?
3. Is there any difference in the economic and educational qualifications of the parents who participate in the children's educational activities and those who do not?
4. What are the reasons for parents not participating in children's educational activities?

Methods and Procedures

To complete this research and find out the real reasons, the researcher adopted a mixed method approach, some questions were asked to the headteachers through the Likert scale, and some were taken through interviews. To check the performance of the children, the portfolios of the children were checked, and the results of the children whose portfolios were not found were sought from their head teachers. Quantitative data were interpreted using SPSS. The qualitative data were analyzed through NVivo by work cloud and word tree.

Validity and Reliability of Instruments

Two types of questionnaires were prepared; one was a Likert scale, through which questions were asked to the children; the main purpose of the study was to know the parents' involvement in their children's education and the parent's interest in their children's education. This scale was developed in the presence of a panel of experts and then pre-tested

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on 10 public and 10 private elementary-level children; its reliability was checked by SPSS, which was .93, which was excellent. The expert panel was approved, and it was unnecessary to improve it further. The second instrument was semi-structured interviews arranged in the presence of an expert panel; their reliability was also checked by asking questions to some teachers. The expert panel checked the interviews and expressed satisfaction, thus completing both instruments. The third step involved checking the children's portfolio records. When their marks and progress were to be checked, this advice was also given by the expert panel.

Population and Sample of the Study

This research was completed through a survey; public and private elementary schools in Punjab were the target population. The condition of all the schools in Punjab was the same, so only three districts were selected as the study sample through random sampling. Then five public and five private elementary schools were randomly selected from these districts. According to the minimum sampling technique, five students were randomly selected from public and five from private elementary schools. In this way, 10 students were taken as a sample from each district, thus making a total of 30 students as a sample of the study, and 6 head teachers, three from public and three from private selected for interviews randomly; this method was adopted according to suggestions of unbiased sampling technique of researcher Hashim (2010). Thus, the total sample of the research was 30 students of elementary classes, 15 of which were taken from public and 15 private schools, then 3 public and 3 private school head teachers were randomly selected for interviews. In this way, 6 head teachers were interviewed.

Sample of the study

The first stage for the selection of sample schools		
Districts	Public	Private
Bahawalpur	5	5
Multan	5	5
D.G. Khan	5	5
Total	15	15
Head Teachers	3	3
The total sample was selected randomly		
Students		30
Head Teachers		6
Total Sample		36

Results of the Study

Descriptive interpretation of the data obtained from students

Group Statistics					
Factors	School type	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Parents Help in	Private Schools	15	1.6400	.51381	.13266
Homework	Public Schools	15	4.4533	.48678	.12569

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Parents Help in	Private Schools	15	1.4267	.31045	.08016
Pick and Drop	Public Schools	15	4.4267	.68813	.17767
Parents Involve in	Private Schools	15	1.4267	.39905	.10303
School Meetings	Public Schools	15	4.4000	.55032	.14209
Parents Gave	Private Schools	15	1.8133	.49261	.12719
Pocket Money	Public Schools	15	4.2267	.63185	.16314
Parents are Highly	Private Schools	15	1.6000	.37796	.09759
Qualified	Public Schools	15	4.5867	.43731	.11291

Table shows the results of data analyses obtained from students. Students show their views about the factor parents help in homework; private school children show a high mean value (1.6400) instead of public-school children's mean (4.4533). The factor parents help in picking and dropping private schools children had a high mean value (1.4267) instead of public-school children (4.4267). The factor of parents' involvement in schools meeting private school children had a high mean (1.4267) instead of public school (4.4000). Regarding parents giving their children pocket money, private school children show a high mean (1.8133) compared to public schools (4.2267). Regarding the factor of parents being highly qualified, the private school children mean (1.6000) was high compared to the private school mean (4.5867).

Inferential interpretation of the data obtained from students

Factors		t-test for Equality of Means					95% Confidence	
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Interval of the Difference	
							Lower	Upper
Parents Help in Homework	Equal variances assumed	-15.395	28	.000	-2.81333	.18275	-3.18768	-2.43899
	Equal variances not assumed	-15.395	27.919	.000	-2.81333	.18275	-3.18772	-2.43894
Parents Help in Pic and Drop	Equal variances assumed	-15.391	28	.000	-3.00000	.19492	-3.39927	-2.60073
	Equal variances not assumed	-15.391	19.472	.000	-3.00000	.19492	-3.40730	-2.59270
Parents Involve in School	Equal variances assumed	-16.940	28	.000	-2.97333	.17552	-3.33286	-2.61380

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Figure 2-word tree

Results drawn from word cloud and word tree that most parents of children studying in public schools are illiterate or very little literate; they don't know much about their educational activities and put all the responsibility on the teachers. On the contrary, the parents of students studying in private schools were highly qualified. Most government employees knew the importance of education and wanted to get their children government jobs, so they were always active and involved in their children's educational activities. Public school teachers were not much interested in involving the parents of the children because they did not have to charge any fees from the children; whether the parents were satisfied or not was of no concern to the teachers. On the contrary, teachers in private schools have to receive fees, so they always ensure the involvement of parents in any case. The education level of public school teachers was very high, but the education level of private school teachers was very low, but the high results were coming from private schools; this was because the full responsibility for the child's performance was placed in front of the parents. Parents were concerned about their children's performance and gave them extra time or tutoring. But this was not the case in public schools. The teachers took all the responsibility themselves, and parents were not allowed to consult. Parents of children studying in private schools are more socially active, so they feel proud by enrolling their children in high-fee-collecting private educational institutions and describing the child's performance to friends and relatives. Hence, they keep a close eye on their child's academic performance. They meet the teachers themselves and evaluate the child's activities; on the contrary, the parents of children studying in public schools were often from the poor class, so they did not give much importance to education and were busy with their work due to which their children did not get the attention of their parents. Public school teachers motivated children and parents very little towards education because

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parents of children studying in public schools were poor and less educated; most were completely illiterate (Research Question 3). Children whose parents were not interested in their educational activities belonged to public schools. The teachers of public schools considered the involvement of parents as a burden; on the contrary, the teachers of private schools used to call parents a lot and meet with them to motivate them by telling them about the benefits of education. The parents of the children studying in private schools were very rich and social. Parents were often found to be poor and anti-social; they had no interest in their children's education and were busy all day earning a living. The teachers also did not want the involvement of the parents and bore the entire burden of the success and failure of the children themselves (Research Question 4).

Parents of children studying in public schools did not help their children with their homework; on the contrary, parents of children studying in private schools took a keen interest in their homework and helped them. Parents of children studying in private schools used to pick and drop their children themselves; on the contrary, parents of public schools did not take any interest in pick-and-drop; children used to come to school and go home alone. Parents of students studying in private schools participated well in parent-teacher meetings in schools; on the contrary, parents of children studying in public schools never met with school teachers. Parents of students studying in private schools used to give pocket money to their children; on the contrary, children in public schools were deprived of pocket money. Parents of children studying in private schools were highly educated; however, parents of children studying in public schools were not so educated.

Researchers Ahmed et al. (2022) explored in their research entitled "*Rural children's perceptions of parental involvement in their education in Pakistan*" that low-income families considered education useless. They gave no importance to education, and they were less motivated in their child's education; this study results strengthen the recent results of our research. Another study by Wajid et al. (2022) entitled "*Reasons for school dropout at the elementary level; Reflection of teachers and parents of dropped out students*" showed that parents' involvement is necessary for students' education without active participation in parents' dropout ratio increased and education quality decreased. These explorations strengthen our recent exploration that parents' involvement effectively affects child education and academic achievement. Hussain et al. (2022) explored in their research entitled "*Correlation between Organizational Stress and Workload Stress Effect on the Academic Performance of Elementary School Teachers*" that teachers' workload and stress were high; they gave less interest to their students. Hence, parents' involvement in their children's education effectively affects Researchers Ribeiro et al. (2021) stated in their research entitled "*Parental involvement during pandemic times: Challenges and opportunities*" that in private schools, parents are involved more than in public schools. These results strengthen our study results that parents involve more in private schools. They attend parent-teacher meetings more, while no such kind of parent-teacher meeting is seen. Researchers Boylan et al. (2021) also found in their research entitled "*Practicing parental involvement: Heterogeneity in parent involvement structures in charter and traditional public schools*" that parental involvement is higher in private schools than in private schools. These results also strengthen our explored results. The findings of Paul et al. (2021) research entitled "*Does lack of parental involvement affect school dropout among Indian adolescents?*"

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evidence from a panel study" contradicted our results that parents involve equally in public and private schools. Otani (2020) stated in his research entitled "*Parental involvement and academic achievement among elementary and middle school students*" that parental involvement highly affects students' academic achievement. These results strengthen our explored results that parent involvement affected highly students' academic achievement.

Conclusions

It was concluded that children whose parents were more interested in their school activities had better academic achievement.

It was concluded that the parents of the students studying in private schools were more involved in their school activities, and there was more involvement in parent-teacher meetings. In contrast, parents of students studying in public schools took little interest in their school activities.

It was concluded that the parents of students studying in private schools were more socially and economically strong, so they paid more attention to their children's education. Therefore, they were more active in school activities. On the contrary, parents of children studying in public schools were labour. They were busy earning their livelihood and could not pay attention to the children.

It was concluded that children whose parents were not interested in their educational activities belonged to public schools. The teachers of public schools considered the involvement of parents as a burden; on the contrary, the teachers of private schools used to call parents a lot and meet with them to motivate them by telling them about the benefits of education. The parents of the children studying in private schools were very rich and social. Parents were often found to be poor and anti-social; they had no interest in their children's education and were busy all day earning a living. The teachers also did not want the involvement of the parents and bore the entire burden of the success and failure of the children themselves.

It was concluded that parents of children studying in private schools used to help their children with homework; on the contrary, parents of children studying in public schools did not help them with homework. There was a reason why they did not give much importance to education. Parents of children studying in private schools used to pick and drop their children themselves; however, parents of public schools did not seem interested in pick-and-drop. One of the main reasons for this was that they were busy earning their living, and the children's interest in education was low. Parents of children studying in public schools were less interested in parent-teacher meetings; on the contrary, parents of students studying in private schools participated well in parent-teacher meetings in schools. One of the main reasons parents of children studying in public schools did not give pocket money to their children was poverty. Parents of the students studying in private schools used to give pocket money. Parents of children studying in public schools were much poorer and socially weaker; parents studying in private schools were more educated and wealthy and were more proud to present their children's achievements to their friends. Due to this, they seemed to pay more attention to their children's education and had more meetings with the teachers.

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Recommendations

1. It is recommended that teachers of public elementary schools invite parents to participate in their children's education by holding parent-teacher meetings. This will make the results for the children very good.
2. It is recommended that parents of students studying in public schools focus on their children's education, meet with their teachers and know about their children's education and progress.
3. It is recommended that public school teachers inform and motivate the children's parents about the importance of education.

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